

DEVELOPMENT OF LEXICAL COMPETENCE AND VOCABULARY STANDARDS OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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***Abstract.** The process of organizing and carrying out educational activities includes knowledge transfer, its reception, understanding, memorization and practical application. At present time a special importance is drawn to the introduction of new modern technologies, their effective and rational use, and the achievement of high efficiency at all stages of education. The teaching of using modern technologies allows students to independently acquire scientific and theoretical knowledge, to form knowledge, skills and qualifications, and on the basis of this, the scientific outlook of students is formed, and their activity increases. The main goal of all innovative education is to develop a passion for learning in students and turn it into a skill. This educational process implies the active participation of the student in educational activities and the development of his creative abilities. Vocabulary has traditionally not received the attention it deserves, usually lumped together with other types of competence until the 1980s and 1990s, when researchers began to focus on it with greater interest. The given paper also includes the discussion regarding the concept of lexical competence and consideration of lexical researchers conceptualize its dimensions, in particular, the breadth and depth of vocabulary knowledge. Additionally, a particular attention is paid to the data from ongoing cross-sectional research on lexical competence in the upper grades and discuss different ways in which these measures of lexical competence can be measured.*

***Keywords:** lexical competence, breadth of vocabulary, depth of vocabulary knowledge, receptive vocabulary, productive vocabulary.*

It is important to suggest that the richness of vocabulary, the teaching and learning of vocabulary has traditionally been underemphasized in second and foreign language programs. As Richards and Renandia (2002, p. 255) argue, “a key component of language proficiency” is “how well learners can speak, listen, read, and write, which largely provides the basis for understanding”. Language pedagogy and vocabulary continued to play a secondary role even in the 1970s when communicative language teaching emerged.

What is more important, due to the fact that communicative language teaching gradually led to a major rethinking of the role of vocabulary, people began to realize the meaning potential of words and, therefore, their importance for second and foreign language learners (Syam Choudhury, 2010, p. 308). The change began in the late 1980s when pioneering developments in lexicography involved “extensive integration of spoken and written language and the development of sophisticated computer-based access tools” (Carter, 2001, p. 43). Later, vocabulary teaching gained momentum when Lewis (1993) proposed his “lexical approach” to developing learners’ lexical competence. Not only did Lewis expand the concept of vocabulary to include “lexical items,” that is, general groups of words or phrases, but language was not a “lexicalized grammar” but a “grammaticalized lexicon”. In order to understand what lexical competence is, it is important to try to understand what the word knowledge means. Richards (1976) was one of the first applied

linguists to propose the concept of "word awareness", which is knowledge of the extent to which a word is likely to occur in spoken or printed language.

Besides that, changes in the function and status of a word, syntactic behavior associated with a word, constraints on its use according to the base form of the word and its possible derivatives, the network of associations of the word with other words in the language, the semantic meaning of the word, and the various meanings associated with the word should be considered. In essence, supporting this structure of lexical knowledge by Richards, Nation (1990) added pronunciation as an important component that makes pronunciation more complete. Furthermore, Nation (1990) made a clear distinction between receptive and productive vocabulary knowledge, arguing that production involves a higher level of vocabulary knowledge than reception. Nation (2001) later revised his original premise and stated that word knowledge, or in other words lexical competence, involves three types of knowledge:

- (i) Knowledge of Form (oral form, written form, and parts of speech);
- (ii) Knowledge of Meaning (form and meaning, concept, referents, and associations);
- (iii) Knowledge of Usage (grammatical functions, adverbs, and restrictions on use).

Definitely, it should be noted that Dale developed this scale for first language learners. For second language learners, Paribakht and Wesche (1993) developed a vocabulary scale very similar to the scale developed by Dale, but with an additional step: "I can use this word in a sentence."

Undeniably, with these suggestions the author concludes that lexical competence is conceptualized differently by different researchers depending on their views of what constitutes vocabulary knowledge. Common to all views is the understanding that lexical competence is multidimensional and that learning words is a complex and step-by-step process. A common feature of lexicography is the view of lexical competence in terms of a number of easily measurable dimensions. One of the most common views on vocabulary acquisition is that vocabulary acquisition occurs in a developmental process. The basic idea is that verbal knowledge develops in some hierarchical order. In line with the concept of a continuum, Henriksen (1999) proposed a three-dimensional model of lexical competence:

- (i) partial specific knowledge;
- (ii) depth of knowledge
- (iii) sensitive to level of production.

It is not a secret that the first dimension, knowledge of individual parts, is mainly concerned with the breadth or size of vocabulary knowledge, as the learner goes through several stages of partial knowledge from simple word recognition, conceptualized as a kind of journey, to the stage of clear understanding by expanding the knowledge base. However, vocabulary size cannot be the only indicator that helps the author understand the lexical competence of a language user. In this context, the second and third dimensions of Henriksen's model are important.

Moreover, the second dimension, depth of knowledge, refers to the relationship of a word to other words in the vocabulary. The relationships may be paradigmatic (antonymy, synonymy, hyponymy, etc.) or syntagmatic (collocation constraints). The third dimension, the receptive production dimension, refers to the extent to which the learner acquires vocabulary knowledge, as reflected in comprehension and production skills. Receptive vocabulary is larger since it concerns only the ability to understand a lexical item. On the other hand, it concerns the ability to use a lexical item to build a productive vocabulary.

Definitely, vocabulary size is often defined as vocabulary breadth or the number of words a person knows, which is one of the main indicators of lexical competence. Vocabulary breadth is closely related to three interesting questions:

- i) How many words are there in the language in question?
- (ii) How many words does a native speaker know?
- (iii) What vocabulary does a second language learner need?

According to Goulden, Nation, and Reed (1990) listed the number of phrases in Webster's Third New International Dictionary (1963), one of the largest dictionaries of English language. After excluding entries such as proper names and alternative spellings, Goulden, Nation, and Reed (1990) found that the dictionary contained about 54,000-word groups. But this learning goal is impossible for second language learners or even native speakers. A recent study (Nation & Waring, 1997, p. 7) found that the average native English speaker with a school education knows about 20,000 vocabulary words. Although there is considerable variation among individuals, this number is generally accepted, excluding proper names, compounds, abbreviations, etc. Liu and Nation (1985, Beglar & Hunt, 2002) and Nation (1990) found that a second language learner must have a requisite knowledge of at least 3,000 words to achieve 95% coverage of all text. At present time, however, most second language researchers recommend a core vocabulary of at least 3,000 words, and for more specialized needs, a working vocabulary of over 5,000 words (Nation, 1990). Another way to describe lexical competence is to show how well a particular word is known. There is no consensus among second language researchers as to what is meant by depth or quality.

What is more important, Meara (1996) viewed depth of knowledge as the interaction between individual words and perceived depth as the organization of words in a mental network. He believed that depth of lexical knowledge, what he called "organization", indicated the relationships a word might have with other words in the language. Based on the scale proposed by Meara (1996), Reed (1998) identified three types of word relationships: paradigmatic (synonymy, antonymy, hyponym, etc.), syntagmatic (association), and analytic. Students with high vocabularies had denser and more organized networks than students with low vocabularies. The question that arises regarding how these parameters should be measured in order to make useful distinctions between students with different levels of second language proficiency. Samples of lexical competence in high school were controlled to substantiate the ideas. Various measures have been developed to assess lexical competence. Vocabulary was originally measured by two diametrically opposed methods: vocabulary sampling, frequency sampling.

It is known to everyone that in the vocabulary sampling method, words are selected from a dictionary and then the person's vocabulary is estimated by multiplying the number of known word samples by the ratio of the total number of words in the dictionary. For example, for a 20,000-word dictionary from which a sample of 100 words is selected, if a person knows 20 words from the sample, his or her vocabulary size would be 4,000 words ($20 \times 20,000/100$).

However, this method was not successful because the estimated vocabulary size was highly dependent on the size of the vocabulary and the definition of the word in the dictionary (Anderson & Freebody, 1981; Lorge & Chall, 1963). As a result, vocabulary research has tended to use frequency sampling as an alternative method of selecting test items to measure vocabulary size. Anderson and Freebody (1981, p. 23) stated that "frequency is the characteristic of a word that is most closely related to the probability that the word will be known". That is, high-frequency words

are learned relatively early, so that students' knowledge of words at a given frequency level reflects their overall vocabulary size.

Another important factor is the nature of the test format for measuring lexical competence. One format used in checklist tests. This format allows for a large number of words to be tested in a short period of time. The target words were listed with one non-word item for every two real words. Students were asked to check whether they knew them. If any of these non-words were checked, this indicated that the student had overestimated their knowledge or vocabulary.

Moreover, the results of the study discussed above showed that there was a significant difference in the lexical competence of B1 and B1+ students in overall competence. It can be assumed that these differences are mainly due to the different educational environments. The B1+ students were graduates of English language departments and thus had more opportunities to learn a second language than the B1 students. In this study, the B1+ students spent an average of 3 hours studying their second language, and most of the work they did was in English. On the other hand, the B1 students studied their second language on average two hours a week. Thus, the B1+ students had more opportunities to learn and use their second language than the B1 students, and this was certainly reflected in the test results.

By summarizing it should be suggested that since vocabulary acquisition is an ongoing process, cross-sectional studies such as the one that provided some of the data for this article can only measure students' lexical competence at a particular point in time can give a brief description, where the longitudinal studies that provide a more complete description in terms of knowing words that are more useful language.

REFERENCES

1. Anderson, R. K., & Freebody, D. (1981). "Knowledge of the vocabulary." In J. T. Guthrie (Ed.), *Understanding and learning: Reviews of the research* (pp. 77–117). Newark, DE: International Reading Association.
2. Carter, R. (2001). Vocabulary. In Ronald Carter & David Noonan (eds.), *The Cambridge handbook of teaching English to speakers of other languages*. (pp. 42–47). Cambridge: Cambridge School Press.
3. Chapelle, C. A. (1998). Building an inquiry into definition and validity in SLA research. In Bachman, L. F., & Cohen, A. D. (eds.), *The interaction between second language acquisition and language testing research* (pp. 32–70). Cambridge: Cambridge School Press.
4. Dale, E. (1965). "Measuring vocabulary: Methods and key findings". *Elementary English*, Vol. 42, pp. 895–901, 948.
5. Goulden, R., Nation, P., and Reed, J. (1990). "How Big Can a Prescriptive Vocabulary Be?", *Applied Linguistics*, Vol. 11, pp. 341–363.
6. Henriksen, B. (1999). "Three Dimensions of Vocabulary Development". *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, Vol. 21, pp. 303–317.
7. Hunt, A., and Belgar, D. (2002). *Current Research and Practice in Vocabulary Teaching*. In Jack C. Richards and Willie A. Renandía (Eds.), *Language Teaching Methodology: An Anthology of Current Practice* (pp. 258–266). New York: Cambridge School Press.
8. Kucera, H., and Francis, W. N. (1967). *A Computerized Analysis of Contemporary American English*. Rhode Island: Brown School Press.

9. Laufer, Bhatia, and Paul Nation. (1999). "A Vocabulary Test of Controlled Production Ability". *Language Testing*, Vol. 16, No. 1, pp. 33-51.
10. Laufer, B., and Paribakht, T. S. (1998). "The Relationship between Passive and Active Vocabulary: The Impact of Language Learning Context". *Language Learning*, Vol. 48, No. 3, pp. 365-391.
11. Lewis, M. (1993). *The Lexical Approach: The State of ELT and the Way Forward*. Hove, England: Language Teaching Publications.
12. Liu, N., and Nation, I. S. P. (1985). "Factors Influencing Vocabulary Prediction in Context." *RELC Journal*, Vol. 16, pp. 33–42.
13. Sobirov, A. *Language Competence in Continuous Education // Current Issues of Speech Culture and Uzbek Linguistics. Proceedings of the Republican Scientific and Practical Conference – Andijan, 2016. – P. 87.*